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Nonlinear Modeling and Perturbation Analysis of Cell Population Dynamics Under External Factors—A Pilot Study of Low-Level Red Laser Irradiation on Lung Cancer Cells

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Abstract

The development of precise quantitative metrics is essential for characterizing the response of biological systems to external perturbations, enabling a transition from qualitative observation to predictive modeling. In this context, mathematical frameworks can provide insight into the dynamic behavior of cell populations under external stimuli. In this study, a logistic-type growth model was employed to describe wound healing dynamics. A scratch assay protocol was applied to lung cancer cells, and a perturbation-based analytical framework was developed to quantify the influence of external factors. Novel metrics were introduced, including the percentage difference in wound closure at specific time points, the shift in inflection time, and the Average Difference in Wound Closure (ADWC). A pilot experimental study was conducted to evaluate the effect of Low-Level Laser Therapy (LLLT) on cell migration. The proposed model successfully captured the nonlinear dynamics of wound closure and enabled quantitative comparison between control and treated groups. The analysis demonstrated that LLLT enhances cellular activity, leading to a shift in the inflection time by approximately 7.6 h and an increase of 25.4% in wound closure at 24 h compared to the control group. The ADWC metric further confirmed a systematic difference in the overall healing dynamics between conditions. The presented perturbation-based framework provides a rigorous and interpretable tool for quantifying the effects of external stimuli on biological systems. These findings suggest a light-dependent modulation of tumor cell migration in an *in vitro* model, indicating that light exposure may influence cellular behavior under certain conditions. This observation may be relevant for clinical applications involving light, such as photodynamic therapy, particularly in cases of incomplete drug delivery.

Keywords: nonlinear growth kinetics; dynamical systems modeling; inflection time shift; model-based quantification; population growth dynamics; cell migration dynamics; photobiomodulation; cancer cell motility

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1. Introduction

The wound healing (scratch) assay provides a controlled *in vitro* framework for investigating collective cell migration and proliferation by monitoring the closure of a denuded region over time. Originally developed to elucidate the biological processes underlying tissue repair [1,2], this method remains a cornerstone of cell biology due to its versatility and cost-effectiveness [3,4]. Within this experimental context, cell migration is defined

as the translocation of individual cells or clusters, whereas collective migration specifically denotes the coordinated movement of cell sheets that maintain their intercellular connections and collective polarity [5]. Typically, a gap is introduced into a confluent cell monolayer, and the subsequent void closure is documented through high-resolution time-lapse imaging [6].

Understanding metastatic progression, particularly cell migration, is crucial for improving therapeutic strategies and reducing cancer mortality. The wound healing (scratch) assay is widely used to study migration *in vitro*, but it is time-consuming, labor-intensive, and provides limited information [7]. Moreover, the artificial wound often has irregular edges, and standard analyses focus mainly on leading-edge movement or overall wound area, overlooking the behavior of the full cell population [8–10]. To overcome these limitations, advanced tracking methods have been developed to follow individual cells in time-lapse images, providing a more comprehensive view of migration that captures both single-cell trajectories and collective behavior [8]. In parallel, computational approaches have been introduced to better quantify wound closure dynamics. For instance, the Prediction Wound Progression Framework (PWPF) combines deep learning with synthetic data augmentation to enable scalable, predictive modeling of wound healing [7]. Mathematical models, especially partial differential equations (PDEs), further enhance scratch assay analysis by providing mechanistic insight into random and directed cell motion. Integrated with live-cell imaging, these frameworks enable the quantitative distinction between migration and proliferation in wound closure [11]. In this context, Fisher's equation, a classical reaction–diffusion model initially developed for gene propagation, has been widely applied to processes such as wave spreading, tissue growth, wound healing, and tumor progression [12]. Overall, combining such theoretical models with modern computational approaches highlights the ongoing evolution of wound healing analysis.

While wound closure is frequently analyzed descriptively, its temporal evolution reflects the behavior of a nonlinear dynamical system constrained by spatial limitations, intercellular interactions, and resource availability. Consequently, the transition from qualitative observation to rigorous analysis is essential for advancing our understanding of these dynamics. Developing precise metrics to evaluate how external factors influence behavior is of paramount importance, as this enables the objective characterization of cellular responses. This allows researchers to distinguish between subtle variations in migration velocity, directional persistence, and proliferative capacity, a shift critical for both experimental reproducibility and the development of predictive models. By translating biological phenomena into measurable variables, researchers can better predict tissue-level outcomes in response to specific perturbations, ultimately accelerating drug discovery and the design of targeted therapies.

To move beyond descriptive evaluation, this study formulates the temporal evolution of the denuded region as a nonlinear dynamical system governed by a logistic-type growth model [13,14]. Originally introduced in population dynamics, the logistic equation captures processes characterized by initial acceleration followed by saturation due to intrinsic limiting factors such as spatial confinement and contact inhibition. In this framework, closure is expressed as the relative reduction in the initial gap, with the rate described as a balance between linear growth and nonlinear inhibition. This formulation enables a systematic analysis of how external influences modify system behavior through parameter variation.

A particularly relevant external perturbation in modern biomedicine is photostimulation, the controlled application of light to modulate biological activity [15]. Light–tissue interactions influence a broad range of cellular processes, including migration and proliferation, with outcomes strongly dependent on wavelength, intensity, and irradiation duration [15–24]. Current light-based approaches generally fall into two categories: low-level

laser therapy (LLLT), which aims to enhance tissue repair, and photodynamic therapy (PDT), which induces selective cytotoxicity in oncology via photosensitizing agents (PS) [25–30]. While the mechanisms of PDT are well-documented, the direct effects of light irradiation alone, without an exogenous PS, remain insufficiently understood, particularly in malignancy. If the PS fails to localize specifically to cancerous tissue, a condition referred to as incomplete or off-target delivery, the therapeutic efficacy may be compromised [29]. This necessitates a rigorous quantitative investigation into whether low-level light irradiation at wavelengths in the range of 600–1200 nm acts as a perturbation that modifies tumor cell migration and proliferation dynamics. In this spectral region, cytochrome-c oxidase serves as a primary mitochondrial chromophore [16,17,31,32], potentially influencing signaling pathways that regulate growth and motility.

The primary aim of this work is to introduce a quantitative framework for analyzing cell population dynamics under external perturbations. We hypothesize that by employing a logistic growth model, the kinetic rate of migration can be effectively decoupled from the final saturation state of the monolayer. Within this context, we propose novel metrics to evaluate global healing efficiency, hypothesizing that these parameters offer superior sensitivity to treatment-induced changes compared to traditional descriptive endpoints. To illustrate the utility of this framework, low-level laser therapy (LLLT) is employed as a representative experimental perturbation. The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the proposed modeling approach, Section 3 reports the experimental results, and Section 4 discusses the implications, limitations and future applications of quantitative methods in wound healing assays.

2. Developing a Mathematical Model to Quantify the Influence of External Factors on Cell Population Dynamics

2.1. The Influence of an External Factor on the % Wound Closure

For a quantitative analysis, a logistic-type growth model is proposed. This model, originally derived from population dynamics, is commonly employed to describe the evolution of biological systems where growth initially accelerates and subsequently slows due to intrinsic limiting factors [13]. In the case of the wound healing process, the system is monitored as the percentage of wound closure over time and can be interpreted as a collective response involving cell migration into the scratched area. The percentage of wound closure at an arbitrary moment t is defined as follows [33]:

$$\varepsilon = \% \text{ wound closure} = \frac{A_0 - A_t}{A_0} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where A_0 is the total area at the cell-free gap and A_t the remaining gap area at the moment t . The % wound closure is denoted as ε (the metric is therefore based on wound area). The quantity $(A_0 - A_t)/A_0$ defines the normalized reduction in the initial wound area, taking values in the interval $[0, 1]$. This normalization ensures that the result is independent of the initial area A_0 , allowing for direct comparison between experiments with different initial wound sizes. The multiplication by 100% is a conventional scaling that expresses this ratio as a percentage, improving interpretability without altering the underlying mathematical meaning.

At the initial stages of the process, we expect an accelerated closure of the wound. However, as time progresses, the availability of space diminishes and cell–cell contact increases, ultimately restricting further expansion. These constraints lead to a saturation-like effect in the wound healing curve. This behavior can be approximated using the differential equation below [13,14]

$$\frac{d\varepsilon}{dt} = \lambda\varepsilon - k\varepsilon^2 \tag{2}$$

Equation (2) balances a linear stimulatory term with a nonlinear inhibitory term, modeling the interplay between cell migration and biological saturation. Here, $\varepsilon(t)$ denotes the percentage of wound closure at time t , λ is the effective growth rate, and the term $k\varepsilon^2$ accounts for the decreasing healing efficiency due to confluency and other biological limitations. For small ε -values (i.e., the initial stages of wound closure), we expect an exponential increase of ε . As the time passes, the rate of change $d\varepsilon/dt$ decreases tending to a limit value when it becomes zero. This limit value is $\varepsilon_{max} = \lambda/k = 100\%$. The analytical solution to Equation (2), which describes a sigmoidal (S-shaped) curve, is given by (see also Appendix A):

$$\varepsilon(t) = \frac{\varepsilon_{max}}{1 + ae^{-\lambda t}} \tag{3}$$

where $a = \frac{\varepsilon_{max}}{\varepsilon_0} - 1$ and ε_0 the initial percentage of closure at $t = 0$. Equation (3) is not defined if considering $\varepsilon_0 = 0$, therefore ε_0 is considered as a free parameter in the curve fitting process. Although the wound is fully open at $t = 0$ and thus the biological expectation is $\varepsilon(0) = 0\%$, the logistic model expressed in Equation (3) requires a nonzero initial value ε_0 to remain mathematically defined. Specifically, setting $\varepsilon_0 = 0$ would lead to a division by zero or an undefined logarithmic term during model derivation, making the analytical solution invalid. From a modeling perspective, ε_0 is treated as an effective parameter that accommodates both the biological lag phase and the resolution limits of image-based quantification. In practical terms, immediately after scratching, cells may begin to polarize, secrete signaling molecules, and activate migratory pathways, processes that are not instantaneously reflected in the measurable wound closure area. Additionally, segmentation inaccuracies or image thresholding may register a minimal apparent closure at early time points. Therefore, ε_0 is retained as a small, nonzero fitting parameter, ensuring a mathematically valid solution while capturing early dynamics in a physiologically meaningful way.

Let \mathcal{X} denote an external factor that induces small perturbations in the parameters a and λ . A first-order parametric perturbation analysis is then carried out as follows:

$$a \rightarrow a + \delta a \text{ and } \lambda \rightarrow \lambda + \delta \lambda \tag{4}$$

where $|\delta \lambda| \ll \lambda$ and $|\delta a| \ll a$. In this case, under the influence of the factor \mathcal{X} , the following expressions are obtained:

$$\varepsilon_{\mathcal{X}}(t) = \frac{\varepsilon_{max}}{1 + (a + \delta a)e^{-(\lambda + \delta \lambda)t}} \tag{5}$$

In addition, consider the function $f(\delta a, \delta \lambda)$:

$$f(\delta a, \delta \lambda) = \frac{\varepsilon_{max}}{1 + (a + \delta a)e^{-(\lambda + \delta \lambda)t}} \tag{6}$$

We will perform a Taylor series expansion centered at $(0, 0)$. The first order approximation is:

$$f(\delta a, \delta \lambda) \approx f(0, 0) + \frac{\partial f}{\partial (\delta a)} \delta a + \frac{\partial f}{\partial (\delta \lambda)} \delta \lambda \tag{7}$$

In Equation (7):

$$f(0, 0) = \frac{\varepsilon_{max}}{D} \tag{8}$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial f}{\partial(\delta a)} \right|_{(0,0)} = -\frac{\varepsilon_{max}e^{-\lambda t}}{D^2} \tag{9}$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial f}{\partial(\delta \lambda)} \right|_{(0,0)} = \frac{at\varepsilon_{max}e^{-\lambda t}}{D^2} \tag{10}$$

where

$$D = 1 + ae^{-\lambda t} \tag{11}$$

Using Equations (9)–(11), Equation (7) is written as follows:

$$f(\delta a, \delta \lambda) \approx \frac{\varepsilon_{max}}{1 + ae^{-\lambda t}} - \frac{\varepsilon_{max}e^{-\lambda t}}{(1 + ae^{-\lambda t})^2} \delta a + \frac{at\varepsilon_{max}e^{-\lambda t}}{(1 + ae^{-\lambda t})^2} \delta \lambda \tag{12}$$

The variation in the response due to the external perturbation is defined as $\delta\varepsilon = f(\delta a, \delta \lambda) - f(0, 0)$. Thus, the change in the percentage due to the effect of the external factor \mathcal{X} can be expressed as:

$$\delta\varepsilon \approx -\frac{\varepsilon_{max}e^{-\lambda t}}{(1 + ae^{-\lambda t})^2} \delta a + \frac{at\varepsilon_{max}e^{-\lambda t}}{(1 + ae^{-\lambda t})^2} \delta \lambda \tag{13}$$

2.2. The Influence of an External Factor in the Inflection Point

The inflection time in the logistic curve is obtained by locating where the second derivative vanishes, i.e., where curvature changes sign. The differential Equation (2) can also be written as follows:

$$\frac{d^2\varepsilon}{dt^2} = \frac{d\varepsilon}{dt}(\lambda - 2k\varepsilon) \tag{14}$$

Thus, $\frac{d^2\varepsilon}{dt^2} = 0$ when $\varepsilon = \lambda/2k$. In addition, by setting $\frac{d\varepsilon}{dt} = 0$ in Equation (2), where $\varepsilon = 100\%$, we conclude that $\lambda/k = 100\%$. Therefore, the inflection point is exactly at $\varepsilon = 50\%$. By setting this value in Equation (3), we can easily conclude that:

$$t_{inf} = \frac{1}{\lambda} \ln(a) \tag{15}$$

Using the same methodology presented in Section 2.1 to analyze the influence of an external factor \mathcal{X} , we obtain:

$$t_{inf} + \delta t = \frac{1}{\lambda + \delta \lambda} \ln(a + \delta a) \tag{16}$$

In addition, using a Taylor series expansion for $\frac{1}{\lambda + \delta \lambda}$ and $\ln(a + \delta a)$ and keeping only the linear terms we conclude that:

$$\frac{1}{\lambda + \delta \lambda} \approx \frac{1}{\lambda} - \frac{\delta \lambda}{\lambda^2} \tag{17}$$

$$\ln(a + \delta a) \approx \ln(a) + \frac{\delta a}{a} \tag{18}$$

Using Equations (17) and (18), Equation (16) can be written as follows:

$$t_{inf} + \delta t = \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} - \frac{\delta \lambda}{\lambda^2} \right) \left(\ln(a) + \frac{\delta a}{a} \right) \tag{19}$$

Finally, the term $\frac{\delta \lambda}{\lambda^2} \frac{\delta a}{a}$ can be neglected since $\delta \lambda \delta a \cong 0$, leading to the following form:

$$t_{inf} + \delta t \approx \frac{\ln(a)}{\lambda} + \frac{1}{\lambda} \frac{\delta a}{a} - \frac{\ln(a)}{\lambda^2} \delta \lambda \tag{20}$$

Or,

$$\delta t \approx \frac{1}{\lambda} \frac{\delta a}{a} - \frac{\ln(a)}{\lambda^2} \delta \lambda \tag{21}$$

2.3. The Influence of an External Factor in the Area Under the Logistic Curve

Additionally, the results can be further quantified by calculating the difference between the areas under the logistic curves for the control dataset and the dataset in which the factor \mathcal{X} is applied. In particular,

$$\text{Area difference} = \left| \int_0^T \varepsilon(t) dt - \int_0^{T_{\mathcal{X}}} \varepsilon_{\mathcal{X}}(t) dt \right| \tag{22}$$

where $\varepsilon(t)$ and $\varepsilon_{\mathcal{X}}(t)$ denote the percentage of wound closure for the control sample and for the sample in which the external factor is applied, respectively. In addition, T and $T_{\mathcal{X}}$ represent the total duration of the phenomenon in each case. In addition, the term:

$$\bar{\varepsilon} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \varepsilon(t) dt \tag{23}$$

represents the average value of the $\varepsilon(t)$ function in the domain $0 \leq t \leq T$. To calculate the area difference, the following integral should be determined:

$$I = \int_0^T \varepsilon dt = 100 \int_0^T \frac{1}{1 + ae^{-\lambda t}} dt \tag{24}$$

Let $u = e^{\lambda t} \Rightarrow du = \lambda e^{\lambda t} dt = \lambda u dt$. Thus, $dt = \frac{du}{\lambda u}$. When $t = 0$, $u = 1$ and when $t = T$, $u = e^{\lambda T}$. So, the integral becomes:

$$I = 100 \int_1^{e^{\lambda T}} \frac{1}{1 + \frac{a}{u}} \frac{du}{\lambda u} = \frac{100}{\lambda} \int_1^{e^{\lambda T}} \frac{1}{u + a} du = \frac{100}{\lambda} [\ln(u + a)]_1^{e^{\lambda T}} \tag{25}$$

Finally, Equation (25) results in:

$$I = \frac{100}{\lambda} \ln\left(\frac{e^{\lambda T} + a}{1 + a}\right) \tag{26}$$

Thus,

$$\text{Area difference} = \left| \frac{100}{\lambda} \ln\left(\frac{e^{\lambda T} + a}{1 + a}\right) - \frac{100}{\lambda_{\mathcal{X}}} \ln\left(\frac{e^{\lambda_{\mathcal{X}} T} + a_{\mathcal{X}}}{1 + a_{\mathcal{X}}}\right) \right| \tag{27}$$

Here, λ and a are the parameters of the logistic curve (Equation (3)) for the control group, while $\lambda_{\mathcal{X}}$ and $a_{\mathcal{X}}$ correspond to the group under the influence of the factor \mathcal{X} . In addition, the difference between the average values for the control and the treated sample, denoted as the average difference in wound closure (ADWC), can be calculated as follows:

$$\text{ADWC} = \left| \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \varepsilon(t) dt - \frac{1}{T_{\mathcal{X}}} \int_0^{T_{\mathcal{X}}} \varepsilon_{\mathcal{X}}(t) dt \right| \tag{28}$$

In the special case, where $T_{\mathcal{X}} \approx T$, the ADWC becomes:

$$ADWC = \frac{100}{T} \left| \frac{1}{\lambda} \ln \left(\frac{e^{\lambda T} + a}{1 + a} \right) - \frac{1}{\lambda \chi} \ln \left(\frac{e^{\lambda \chi T} + a \chi}{1 + a \chi} \right) \right| \quad (29)$$

Equations (13), (21), (28) and (29) will be used as quantitative metrics to estimate the potential influence of LLLT on lung cancer cells.

3. A Pilot Study on H1975 Lung Cancer Cells

3.1. Materials and Methods

3.1.1. Study Design

This study was designed as an in vitro intervention study to evaluate the effects of the tested treatments on cell behavior under controlled laboratory conditions. In each experiment, treated and control groups were processed in parallel under the same experimental conditions. Experiments were repeated independently three times to ensure reproducibility. To minimize potential batch effects, comparisons between groups were made within the same experimental run whenever possible, using the same cell passage range, culture conditions, reagent preparations, incubation times, and imaging settings. All wound-healing images for a given experiment were acquired using the same microscope and magnification and were analyzed using the same ImageJ 1.53k procedure (see details in the following sections). To reduce image-analysis bias, wound areas were assessed using a predefined and consistent analysis workflow. Potential confounding variables were controlled by maintaining identical experimental conditions across groups, including cell seeding density, medium composition, incubation conditions, timing of scratch generation, treatment exposure, and image acquisition time points.

3.1.2. Cell Culture

In this study, we focused on lung cancer cell lines, specifically the H1975 cell line. Commercially available human lung cancer cells (NCI-H1975, American Type Culture Collection) were used in this study and cultured according to standard protocols. Cells were maintained at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂ in RPMI-1640 medium supplemented with 1% antibacterial-antimycotic solution. Before use in the experiments, cells were screened for mycoplasma contamination and found to be negative. To minimize phenotypic variability and avoid alterations associated with prolonged culture, all experiments were conducted using cells between passages 8 and 10. After cell attachment in 96-well plates, the culture medium was replaced with fresh medium containing 2% fetal bovine serum (FBS) to induce a low-serum condition aimed at reducing proliferation, followed by incubation for 24 h. Although no independent short tandem repeat (STR) authentication was performed in the present study, the cells were obtained from a certified repository and handled under standard laboratory conditions. All cultures were routinely monitored by visual inspection to exclude contamination, and no evidence of contamination was observed during the experiments.

3.1.3. Laser Treatment

The PL252 laser source (Thorlabs) was used as the excitation light in all experiments. The laser emitted visible red light with a nominal wavelength of 639 nm (wavelength range: 630–643 nm). The output beam was collimated, producing a diameter of 3 mm at a distance of 5 cm from the aperture, with an optical power of 4.5 mW. Prior to irradiation, the culture medium was replaced with 100 µL of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), and the cells were exposed to light for 2 min, corresponding to a defined energy density. The energy dose (denoted as D) in J/cm² is calculated as follows:

$$D = \frac{Pt}{A} \quad (30)$$

where P is the power of the light, t is the duration of exposure, and $A = \pi d^2/4$ is the beam area (with d representing the beam diameter). For $P = 4.5$ mW, $t = 120$ s and $d = 3$ mm, we conclude that $D = 7.6$ J/cm². Following irradiation, the cells were returned to the incubator and cultured for 48 h in total. All procedures were performed inside a biosafety cabinet with the hood light switched off, while the laboratory room lights remained on. Regarding irradiance uniformity, the laser spot was adjusted to fully cover the well area, ensuring homogeneous exposure across the cell monolayer, and all irradiations were performed under identical geometric and alignment conditions to minimize spatial variability in the delivered dose.

3.1.4. Wound Healing/Scratch Assay

Cells were detached from the tissue culture dish following standard procedures for cell passage. They were then counted and seeded at a density of 40×10^3 cells per well in a 96-well culture plate, with 150 μ L of pre-warmed culture medium added to each well. The cells were allowed to adhere and form a monolayer over 24 h. After this period, the cells were starved by replacing the medium with 150 μ L of culture medium containing 2% FBS per well. Following 24 h of starvation, the wells were washed with PBS, and a scratch was made across the bottom of each well using a 1 mm pipette tip to create a wound. The monolayer was then washed with 100 μ L PBS to remove detached cells and replenished with fresh 2% FBS medium.

The same procedure used for the control cells was applied to the irradiated cells, with the key difference being that irradiation was performed immediately after scratch creation, ensuring that the laser stimulus was applied at the onset of the wound-healing process and coincided with the initial stages of collective migration. This timing captures the early dynamical response of the cell monolayer, when motility-driven rearrangements and signaling pathways governing closure are first activated. After irradiation, 150 μ L of 2% FBS medium was added to each well, and the plate was incubated. Cell images were captured at 0, 16, 24, and 48 h to monitor wound healing. The irradiation setup involved mounting the laser source vertically on a stand inside the hood, aimed directly at the 96-well plate. The laser was powered externally via a portable power bank located outside the hood. Images were acquired using an optical microscope (Motic AE2000, Motic Instruments Inc., Xiamen, China) with a 4 \times objective lens at 0, 16, 24, and 48 h to monitor wound closure over time. Wound images were analyzed using ImageJ 1.53k/Fiji (National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, MD, USA). No automated thresholding algorithm was applied. Instead, the cell-free wound area at each time point was manually outlined using the Freehand Selection tool, and wound closure was calculated relative to the initial wound area at 0 h. Image analysis was performed by an investigator blinded to the experimental group. To assess inter-operator variability, a subset of images was independently analyzed by a second investigator, with high agreement between measurements. The associated measurement uncertainty, primarily arising from manual delineation of wound boundaries, was found to be low and comparable to the observed inter-operator agreement, and is therefore considered negligible relative to the biological variability between samples. The imaging conditions were kept strictly constant across all time points, with identical magnification, field-of-view, and microscope alignment.

3.1.5. Statistics

Each group (control and laser-treated for 24 h) consisted of nine measurements, derived from three independent experiments, each including three scratches per condition

(for both control and laser-treated, 24 h post-treatment). A hierarchical bootstrap approach was employed to account for the nested structure of the experimental data [34]. The dataset consisted of independent biological replicates (experiments performed on different days), each including multiple technical replicates (three scratches per condition). Resampling was performed at two levels in order to preserve the hierarchical organization of the data. For each bootstrap iteration, experiments were first sampled with replacement from the set of independent experiments. Subsequently, for each selected experiment, the corresponding technical replicates (scratch measurements) were resampled with replacement. All resampled observations (% wound closure values) within each group were pooled, and the arithmetic mean of these values was calculated for both control and laser-treated conditions. The treatment effect was defined as the difference between the mean % wound closure of the two groups. A total of 10,000 bootstrap iterations were performed to generate the empirical distribution of the treatment effect. The mean effect size and the corresponding 95% confidence interval were estimated from this distribution using the percentile method (2.5th and 97.5th percentiles). This approach allows for robust estimation of uncertainty while accounting for both between-experiment variability and within-experiment variation, without violating the dependence structure of the data. All statistical analyses were performed using custom-written scripts in MATLAB (R2021a).

3.1.6. Curve Fitting

Model parameters were estimated using nonlinear least-squares regression by minimizing the sum of squared errors between experimental measurements and model predictions. The fitting procedure was implemented in MATLAB (R2021a, MathWorks, Natick, MA, USA) using the built-in nonlinear optimization function (`lsqcurvefit`). Initial parameter values were selected based on direct visual inspection of the experimental data trends to ensure physically reasonable starting points. The robustness of the fitting procedure was verified by testing multiple initial guesses, confirming convergence to consistent parameter values. No hard constraints were imposed on the parameters, except for physically meaningful bounds enforcing positivity where required. In particular, ε_0 was treated as a free fitting parameter and was simultaneously optimized within the nonlinear regression framework. The carrying capacity ε_{max} was not treated as an independent fitting parameter, but was fixed by the definition of the normalized wound-closure metric (Equation (1)). Under this formulation, complete wound closure corresponds by construction to $\varepsilon = 100\%$, and therefore $\varepsilon_{max} = 100\%$ follows directly from the normalization rather than representing a free biological parameter. This choice ensures consistency across all experimental conditions and avoids unnecessary parameter redundancy in the model. Importantly, comparisons between conditions (e.g., in λ) remain robust, as they are based on relative kinetic differences and are not influenced by the fixed upper bound imposed by the normalization. The resulting parameter set corresponded to the global minimum of the least-squares objective within the tested initialization space.

3.2. Results

As already mentioned in Section 3.1, two experimental groups were prepared: a control group and a laser-treated group. Following the wound healing assay, selected wells in the treatment group were exposed to laser irradiation for 2 min, corresponding to an energy density of 7.6 J/cm^2 , while control wells received no irradiation (Figure 1). The 2 min irradiation protocol was chosen based on previous studies showing that energy densities of $1\text{--}10 \text{ J/cm}^2$ promote cellular migration without inducing phototoxic effect [15,17,20,35–41]. For an initial evaluation regarding the influence of LLLT on cancer cells, we performed three individual experiments, each containing three scratch wounds, recording the % wound

closure for both laser-treated and untreated samples after 24 h. The initial wound area at $t = 0$ and the wound area at $t = 24$ h for the two groups, along with the percentage differences in each case, are presented in Table 1.

Figure 1. The mean \pm standard deviation values of the percentage of wound closure for the control and laser-treated groups are presented based on the numerical data in Table 1.

Table 1. Control group and laser-treated group at $t = 0$ and $t = 24$ h. The corresponding initial wound areas (A_0) were 7.57 ± 0.71 mm² for the control group and 6.89 ± 2.34 mm² for the laser-treated group. Quantitative analysis shows a significant difference in wound closure between conditions. At 24 h, the percentage of wound closure was $\epsilon = 34.01 \pm 12.32\%$ for the control group and $\epsilon_1 = 60.72 \pm 11.07\%$ for the laser-treated group.

	Control Group			Laser-Treated Group		
	A (mm ²) t = 0	A (mm ²) t = 24 h	ϵ (% Wound Closure)	A (mm ²) t = 0	A (mm ²) t = 24 h	ϵ (% Wound Closure)
1st Experiment	8.1	4.1	49.4	7.2	1.9	73.6
	7.7	5.0	35.1	6.6	3.0	54.5
	7.1	4.8	32.4	7.9	2.2	72.2
2nd Experiment	7.4	4.8	35.1	4.0	2.0	50.0
	6.6	4.9	25.8	7.0	1.9	72.9
	7.1	5.9	16.9	3.6	2.1	41.7
3rd Experiment	8.4	5.0	40.5	11.4	4.9	57.0
	8.7	4.1	52.3	8.4	3.2	61.9
	7.0	5.7	18.6	5.9	2.2	62.7

The initial wound area (A_0), measured prior to laser irradiation, showed variability between experiments due to manual scratch generation. The mean A_0 values were 7.57 ± 0.71 mm² for the control group and 6.89 ± 2.34 mm² for the laser group. In the present study, wound closure is quantified as percentage wound closure, defined as $(A_0 - A_t)/A_0 \times 100$. This formulation inherently normalizes the measurements with respect to the initial wound size, rendering the resulting metric mathematically independent of the absolute value of A_0 . Consequently, comparisons between experimental conditions are based on relative closure dynamics rather than absolute wound dimensions. Under this normalization, proportional differences in A_0 are effectively canceled, and variability in initial scratch width does not bias the calculated percentage closure, provided that measurements remain internally consistent within each scratch. Nevertheless, it is acknowledged

that substantial variability in A_0 may introduce secondary effects, such as geometric or edge-related influences on migration behavior.

For the untreated sample (control group), $\varepsilon = 34.01 \pm 12.32\%$ while for the laser-treated sample $\varepsilon_L = 60.72 \pm 11.07\%$. The results presented in Table 1 are also comparatively shown in Figure 1. In the laser-treated samples, the wound was consistently more than 50% closed at 24 h, a substantially higher percentage than in the control group.

Figure 2a presents the raw experimental measurements of percentage wound closure obtained from the three independent experiments, each consisting of three scratches per condition (control and laser-treated after 24 h). The individual data points are shown in order to explicitly illustrate the variability within and between experiments, without any aggregation beyond the experimental grouping. This visualization provides a direct representation of the underlying data structure and highlights the dispersion of measurements across replicates.

Figure 2b presents the results of the hierarchical bootstrap analysis of the treatment effect (Laser–Control) in terms of percentage wound closure. In this procedure, experiments and individual scratch measurements were resampled with replacement to preserve the nested structure of the data (three independent experiments with three measurements per condition). For each of 10,000 bootstrap iterations, the mean difference in % wound closure between laser-treated and control groups was computed. The resulting distribution represents the range of effect sizes compatible with the observed data under repeated resampling. The analysis yielded a mean treatment effect of 26.60% with a 95% confidence interval of 18.03% to 35.50%, indicating that virtually all bootstrap realizations support a positive treatment effect. The distribution is strongly shifted towards positive values, confirming a consistent increase in wound closure under laser treatment across resampled datasets, while its spread reflects uncertainty arising from both inter-experiment and intra-experiment variability.

Figure 2c summarizes the same bootstrap results in terms of the point estimate and its associated uncertainty. The central value represents the mean treatment effect (Laser for 24 h–Control), while the error bars correspond to the 95% confidence interval obtained from the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of the bootstrap distribution. The horizontal reference line at zero indicates the absence of a treatment effect. Since the confidence interval lies entirely above zero, the results indicate that the observed increase in wound closure under laser treatment is robust to resampling of both experiments and individual measurements, supporting a consistent positive treatment effect within the limits of the available dataset.

Therefore, LLLT can be considered a valid external factor \mathcal{X} that induces changes in the dynamical system of lung cancer cells. At this point, it should be noted once again that the external factor \mathcal{X} (LLL) is not introduced as an additive term, but is instead treated as a perturbation that modifies the parameters of the logistic-type model, i.e., $a \rightarrow a + \delta a$ and $\lambda \rightarrow \lambda + \delta \lambda$ (see also Equation (4)), so that its effect is implicitly incorporated through parameter variations between control and irradiated condition. Based on this, the evolution of the system was recorded for both control and laser-treated samples in three different cases, as shown in Figure 3A.

Time-course analysis (0–48 h) was also performed in one representative experiment. The parameters a and λ (Figure 3A) are treated as time-independent constants within the logistic formulation; however, they should be interpreted as effective parameters that integrate the combined influence of underlying biological processes, which may vary over time. The reported parameter values should be interpreted as effective descriptors of wound-healing dynamics under the present experimental conditions, rather than as uniquely identifiable mechanistic parameters.

Figure 2. (a) Raw percentage wound closure data from three independent experiments (three scratches per condition), showing variability across replicates. (b) Hierarchical bootstrap distribution of the treatment effect (Laser–Control) based on 10,000 resamples, preserving the nested data structure. (c) Mean treatment effect with 95% confidence interval, indicating a consistent positive effect of laser treatment.

Representative images of the wound healing process are also shown in Figure 3B. The distance between the laser source and the samples was maintained constant across all experiments to ensure dose consistency. Wound healing was quantified using Equation (1). A complete closure was observed at approximately 48 h in all cases (both the control and laser-treated samples were fully closed). The initial wound area, denoted as A_0 , is shown on each graph (measured in mm^2). For the samples from the control group presented

in Figure 3, the initial wound areas were 8.1 mm², 7.7 mm², and 7.1 mm², while for the irradiated samples, they were 7.2 mm², 6.6 mm², and 7.9 mm².

Figure 3. (A) Quantitative data from both the control and irradiated groups were collected over time. These results clearly demonstrate the effect of laser treatment on wound healing, showing accelerated closure in the irradiated samples compared to controls. (B) Representative images of the wound healing process ((a–c) control group, (d–f) laser treated group).

In every case, Equation (3) accurately fit the experimental data. The fitting parameters λ and a are indicated on each graph, along with the R-squared coefficient (which was close to 1 in every case, demonstrating the accuracy of the fit). Therefore, this model accurately captures the experimental wound healing data both without irradiation and under light exposure as expected, reflecting the initial acceleration followed by the saturation commonly observed in biological tissue regeneration. As already mentioned, from the quantitative data in Figure 3, it is clear that laser treatment enhanced wound closure. The mean values of % wound closure for the data presented in Figure 3 were calculated and fitted to Equation (3), resulting in $a = 53.01$ and $\lambda = 0.151 \text{ h}^{-1}$ for the control group samples and $a_L = 50.94$, $\lambda_L = 0.193 \text{ h}^{-1}$ for the laser-treated samples (here, the symbol L refers to the laser-treated group, with L representing the external factor \mathcal{X}).

The mean values and the curves plotted using these values and Equation (3) are presented for comparison in Figure 4. The effect of laser treatment on wound healing is clearly evident. By considering $\delta a = a - a_L = 2.07$ and $\delta \lambda = \lambda - \lambda_L = 0.042 \text{ h}^{-1}$, Equation (13) at $t = 24 \text{ h}$ results in:

$$\delta \varepsilon|_{24\text{h}} \approx -\varepsilon_{max} \frac{e^{-\lambda t}}{(1 + ae^{-\lambda t})^2} \delta a + \varepsilon_{max} \frac{ate^{-\lambda t}}{(1 + ae^{-\lambda t})^2} \delta \lambda = 25.4\% \tag{31}$$

Figure 4. The mean ε -values for the data presented in Figure 3 were calculated for both the untreated and laser-irradiated samples. The mean data for each case were then fitted to the logistic model (Equation (3)). This comparative analysis clearly demonstrates the effect of laser irradiation on wound healing.

Furthermore, the difference in the inflection point results in the following: (Equation (21)):

$$\delta t \approx \frac{1}{\lambda} \frac{\delta a}{a} - \frac{\ln(a)}{\lambda^2} \delta \lambda = 7.6 \text{ h} \tag{32}$$

The results can be further quantified using the ADWC. In the case presented in this paper $T \approx T_L$, i.e., 48 h.

Figure 5 represents the time-integrated difference between the logistic wound-closure curves of the control and treated groups. In particular, the reported area difference corresponds to the integral of the vertical separation between the two fitted curves over the experimental time interval. Since wound closure is expressed as a percentage (dimensionless), this integrated quantity is expressed in units of time (hours) and provides a cumulative measure of the overall acceleration induced by the treatment.

Figure 5. The difference in area between the logistic curves for the laser-treated and control samples is shown for the case in Figure 4. Since the percentage of wound closure is dimensionless, the area is expressed in hours. This difference quantifies how the treatment accelerates the early phase of healing, allowing the wound to reach higher closure levels more quickly.

The ADWC is obtained using two methods. First by numerically calculating the area differences in Figure 5 (the result is approximately 11.9%). Second, using the analytical expression provided in the manuscript (Equation (29)):

$$ADWC = \frac{100}{T} \left[\frac{1}{\lambda_L} \ln \left(\frac{e^{\lambda_L T} + a_L}{1 + a_L} \right) - \frac{1}{\lambda} \ln \left(\frac{e^{\lambda T} + a}{1 + a} \right) \right] \quad (33)$$

With:

$a = 53.01$ and $\lambda = 0.151 \text{ h}^{-1}$ (Control group)

$a_L = 50.94$, $\lambda_L = 0.193 \text{ h}^{-1}$ (Laser treated group)

$$ADWC = \frac{100}{48 \text{ h}} \left[\frac{1}{0.193 \text{ h}^{-1}} \ln \left(\frac{e^{0.193 \text{ h}^{-1} \cdot 48 \text{ h}} + 50.94}{1 + 50.94} \right) - \frac{1}{0.151 \text{ h}^{-1}} \ln \left(\frac{e^{0.151 \text{ h}^{-1} \cdot 48 \text{ h}} + 53.01}{1 + 53.01} \right) \right]$$

$$ADWC = \frac{100}{48} [27.558 - 21.827] = 11.9\%$$

Area difference is measured in h (or equivalently h·%). The ADWC has units of area difference divided by T (which has units of time); therefore, it is expressed in percentage (%).

ADWC provides a time-integrated measure of the overall deviation between control and treated conditions in wound closure dynamics. The value of approximately 11.9% reflects a cumulative effect of the external stimulus across the entire observation period, rather than a localized difference at a single time point. Although this magnitude may appear modest in absolute terms, it captures the total impact of the treatment on the overall experimental procedure. In this sense, ADWC integrates temporal variations in cellular response and provides a robust descriptor of treatment-induced changes. As indicated in the results, this integrated deviation is associated with an altered closure trajectory and a shift in the timing of maximum migration activity. From a biological perspective, such cumulative differences are relevant in wound healing assays, as they reflect coordinated changes in collective cell motility and population-level behavior.

Physically, these results signify that laser irradiation not only accelerates the rate of wound closure but also sustains higher closure levels throughout the healing period. In

practical terms, this means that cells in the irradiated samples migrate earlier and more efficiently. The calculated increase of approximately 11.9% in mean wound closure, together with the $\delta\varepsilon$ and δt metrics, provides a quantitative measure of the overall biological effects of laser treatment compared to the control condition.

It should be noted that the first-order Taylor approximation is valid under the assumption of small parameter perturbations, i.e., ($|\delta\lambda| \ll \lambda$ and $|\delta a| \ll a$). To assess the validity of this approximation in the present case, the corresponding error was evaluated for the parameter set shown in Figure 4 (i.e., $a = 53.01$ and $\lambda = 0.151 \text{ h}^{-1}$ for the control and $a_L = 50.94$, $\lambda_L = 0.193 \text{ h}^{-1}$ for the laser-treated group). The resulting Taylor approximation error is presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Error of the first-order Taylor approximation.

4. Discussion

The transition from purely descriptive to model-based metrics enables a deeper biophysical interpretation of the wound healing process under various external perturbations. While traditional assays report when a wound closes, our framework quantifies the intensity of the collective response through the proposed metrics (i.e., $\delta\varepsilon$, δt , ADWC). The development of rigorous quantitative mathematical metrics is essential for advancing our understanding of biological processes, as it allows the transition from descriptive observation to the objective and reproducible characterization of cellular responses to external perturbations. By translating complex biological phenomena into quantifiable variables, researchers can better predict tissue-level outcomes and distinguish subtle variations in cellular behavior, which is critical for experimental reproducibility and the development of predictive models. Within this context, the wound healing or scratch assay remains a cornerstone of cell biology because it provides a controlled *in vitro* framework for investigating collective cell migration through the monitoring of gap closure over time. Typically, this process reflects the behavior of a nonlinear dynamical system constrained by spatial limitations and intercellular interactions. Low-level laser therapy (LLLT) serves as a classic and particularly relevant external factor in modern biomedicine, acting as a controlled application of light to modulate biological activity. Despite its common use to enhance tissue repair, there remain significant open questions regarding its direct influence on cell dynamics, particularly in malignancy where the effects of light irradiation without exogenous photosensitizing agents are not yet fully understood.

The specific results of this study, analyzed through the proposed mathematical metrics, provide evidence of how LLLT alters lung cancer cell dynamics. By modeling the temporal evolution of the denuded region as a logistic-type growth system, we found that laser

treatment at an energy density of 7.6 J/cm^2 acts as a formal system perturbation that significantly enhances wound closure. According to the proposed closure difference metric ($\delta\epsilon$), the logistic model estimates a 25.4% enhancement in wound closure for irradiated samples at 24 h. Furthermore, the metric for the inflection point (δt) revealed that the laser-treated cells reached their maximum closure velocity approximately 7.6 h earlier than the control group. Finally, the Average Difference in Wound Closure (ADWC) metric, which integrates the area under the logistic curves over the 48 h duration, quantified a total enhancement of 11.9% in the healing process. These metrics collectively demonstrate that the proposed mathematical framework accurately captures and quantifies the stimulatory effect of LLLT on the migration and proliferation of H1975 lung cancer cells. Previous studies using LLLT with red light reported enhanced migration during wound healing using similar irradiation doses, and their observation of faster wound closure aligns closely with our results [15,17,20,35–41]. This suggests that red light photostimulation may activate similar cellular pathways, such as those involving cytochrome-c oxidase, enhancing migratory capacity in cancer cells.

It is also important to note that the logistic model can be interpreted as an effective macroscopic description of a collectively driven migration process under spatial confinement. The inflection point naturally corresponds to the transition from an initially motility-dominated regime, where cell–cell coordination is limited, to a crowding-limited regime, where progressive reduction in free space leads to a gradual deceleration of wound closure. This behavior is consistent with the expected emergence of nonlinear saturation effects in confluent monolayers, where migration becomes increasingly constrained as the wound area decreases. In this sense, the model parameters acquire a direct physical interpretation linked to the underlying collective dynamics, rather than serving as purely empirical fitting quantities. This further supports the use of logistic formulation as a minimal but physically meaningful representation of wound healing kinetics in the present experimental conditions. Consequently, the logistic form should be regarded as a coarse-grained description of an underlying complex, multi-factor biological process rather than a phenomenological curve fit. Both datasets (control and Laser-treated) are constrained to share the same equilibrium state, while the differences between experimental conditions are encoded in the effective parameters a and λ , which control the initial condition and the characteristic relaxation rate toward saturation, respectively.

From a biological perspective, the present findings provide quantitative insight into how external stimuli can modulate key features of cell migration. The percentage difference in wound closure at selected time points, the shift in inflection time, and the Average Difference in Wound Closure (ADWC) constitute rigorous mathematical criteria for assessing the influence of external perturbations on cell population dynamics. The results of the pilot study suggest enhanced collective migration under low-level laser radiation (LLLR). Although the underlying molecular mechanisms were not investigated, the proposed framework enables a quantitative characterization of these effects, providing a bridge between experimental observations and biologically relevant interpretation. This approach may facilitate the systematic evaluation of external perturbations in cancer-related processes, where altered migration behavior is closely associated with disease progression.

It should be clarified that the primary aim of the present study is not to provide a comprehensive dose–response characterization of low-level laser therapy (LLLT) in cancer cells, but rather to introduce and validate a novel quantitative framework for analyzing wound healing dynamics and extracting robust metrics from time-dependent experimental data. In this context, the biological experiment is intended as a representative and physiologically relevant example demonstrating the applicability of the proposed analytical approach. For this reason, a single non-negligible irradiation condition (639 nm,

7.6 J/cm²) was selected as a characteristic and literature-consistent LLLT dose, rather than performing a full parameter sweep. This choice ensures that the dataset reflects realistic experimental conditions while maintaining emphasis on the methodological contribution of the work.

It is also important to discuss the limitations of the present study. First, there is the absence of a sham-controlled condition, in which samples would undergo identical handling procedures (medium replacement, exposure to ambient conditions, and positioning under the laser setup) without laser activation. While the control group provides a baseline comparison of untreated cellular behavior, it does not fully isolate potential non-specific effects associated with experimental handling. Regarding thermal effects, the applied irradiation parameters (low power and energy density within the typical photobiomodulation range) are generally reported to operate under non-thermal conditions. However, it is acknowledged that even minor temperature fluctuations or handling-induced perturbations cannot be completely excluded in the absence of direct measurement. Future work will therefore incorporate sham-controlled experiments alongside real-time temperature monitoring, in order to rigorously isolate the specific contribution of light irradiation. In addition, a systematic investigation of dose–response relationships will be conducted to further extend the applicability of the proposed analytical framework.

An additional limitation concerns the use of a single cell line, which restricts the generalizability of the findings. Cellular responses to low-level laser therapy (LLLT) are known to be cell-type dependent, particularly in cancer systems characterized by heterogeneous metabolic and migratory behavior. Therefore, caution should be exercised in extrapolating the present results to other cell lines or biological contexts. Future studies will include multiple cell models to assess the robustness and universality of the proposed analytical framework.

Furthermore, the scratch assay itself presents inherent limitations, as it reflects a combined contribution of cell migration and proliferation. In order to reduce mitogenic stimulation while preserving cell viability and adhesion, a low-serum condition (2% FBS) was employed. While this approach is commonly used to suppress proliferation, a residual contribution from proliferation cannot be excluded. However, since all experimental groups were maintained under identical conditions, the comparative analysis and relative differences between treatments remain valid. Nevertheless, this aspect should be considered when interpreting the results. Future work will incorporate complementary experimental approaches, including the use of proliferation inhibitors (e.g., mitomycin C), proliferation markers (such as EdU incorporation or Ki67 staining), and viability assays, to further decouple migratory and proliferative contributions. In addition, a systematic investigation of dose–response relationships will be pursued, enabling a more comprehensive mathematical and experimental characterization of LLLT effects on wound healing dynamics.

The selection of a limited number of time points was motivated by both the characteristics of the experimental data and the need to minimize the impact of measurement noise, which can be particularly pronounced in intermediate stages of scratch assays. From a biological perspective, reducing the frequency of measurements is also advantageous, as repeated handling and imaging may introduce phototoxic effects or other environmental fluctuations that could potentially influence cellular behavior. Despite the sparse temporal sampling, the results demonstrate that the proposed model accurately reproduces the observed wound closure dynamics, indicating its robustness and ability to extract meaningful kinetic parameters even under data-limited conditions. This characteristic further supports the practical applicability of the model, particularly for experimental datasets in which high-resolution temporal sampling is not feasible. However, the relatively small number of temporal data points also constitutes a limitation, as it may affect the statistical robustness

of parameter estimation and reduce the discriminative power between competing models. This constraint arises from the need to minimize prolonged experimental manipulation, which could introduce additional external influences on cell behavior.

Finally, it should be noted that the analytical formulation relies on the assumption of small perturbations in model parameters (i.e., $|\delta\lambda| \ll \lambda$ and $|\delta a| \ll a$), which justifies the use of a first-order Taylor approximation. While this assumption is consistent with the observed parameter variations in the present study, its validity should be carefully evaluated in cases involving larger deviations, where higher-order effects may become significant.

The presented findings indicate a light-induced modulation of cellular behavior in the present in vitro wound-healing model. While such effects may be conceptually comparable to scenarios encountered in photodynamic therapy (PDT), the current study does not investigate photosensitizer-mediated processes or clinical treatment conditions. Therefore, any extrapolation to therapeutic settings should be further investigated. Within the limits of this in vitro pilot framework, the results should be interpreted solely as evidence of a potential light-dependent effect on tumor cell migratory dynamics under controlled experimental conditions. In future investigations, we will utilize these proposed metrics to quantify the effects of different irradiation doses and to explore the dynamics of various other types of cancer cell lines.

5. Conclusions

In this work, we proposed a novel mathematical analysis based on logistic growth modeling, introducing three quantitative metrics to evaluate the influence of external factors on cell population dynamics: the difference in percentage closure, the shift in inflection time, and the Average Difference in Wound Closure (ADWC). A pilot study was conducted using lung cancer cells to assess the applicability and sensitivity of these metrics. The results are promising and suggest that this framework can be extended to quantify the effects of varying doses of low-level laser therapy (LLLT) on cancer cell populations. Furthermore, the proposed methodology can be applied to different cancer cell lines using standardized wound healing (scratch) assay protocols, providing a generalizable tool for quantitative analysis of external perturbations in cellular dynamics.

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Appendix A. The Solution of Equation (2)

We re-arrange differential Equation (2) as follows:

$$\frac{d\varepsilon}{\varepsilon(\lambda - k\varepsilon)} = dt \quad (\text{A1})$$

Using the partial fraction method, we modify the left-hand side of Equation (A1) as follows:

$$\frac{1}{\varepsilon(\lambda - k\varepsilon)} = \frac{1}{\lambda\varepsilon} + \frac{k}{\lambda(\lambda - k\varepsilon)} \quad (\text{A2})$$

We substitute Equation (A2) into Equation (A1) and then integrate both sides:

$$\int \left[\frac{1}{\lambda\varepsilon} + \frac{k}{\lambda(\lambda - k\varepsilon)} \right] d\varepsilon = \int dt \Rightarrow \frac{1}{\lambda} \ln \varepsilon - \frac{1}{\lambda} \ln |\lambda - k\varepsilon| = t + C \quad (\text{A3})$$

Equation (A3) can also be written as follows:

$$\ln \left| \frac{\varepsilon}{\lambda - k\varepsilon} \right| = \lambda t + \lambda C \Rightarrow \frac{\varepsilon}{\lambda - k\varepsilon} = e^{\lambda t} e^{\lambda C} \Rightarrow \frac{\varepsilon}{\lambda - k\varepsilon} = C' e^{\lambda t} \quad (\text{A4})$$

where $C' = e^{\lambda C}$. By solving Equation (A4) with respect to ε we conclude:

$$\varepsilon(t) = \frac{C' \lambda e^{\lambda t}}{1 + C' k e^{\lambda t}} \Rightarrow \varepsilon(t) = \frac{\lambda/k}{1 + \frac{1}{C' k} e^{-\lambda t}} \quad (\text{A5})$$

For $t \rightarrow \infty$, $e^{-\lambda t} \rightarrow 0$ and $\varepsilon \rightarrow \frac{\lambda}{k}$. Therefore, $\varepsilon_{max} = \frac{\lambda}{k}$. In addition, for $t = 0$, $\varepsilon(0) = \frac{\lambda C'}{C' k + 1}$. Thus, $C' = \frac{\varepsilon(0)}{\lambda - k\varepsilon(0)}$ and Equation (A5) is modified as follows:

$$\varepsilon(t) = \frac{\varepsilon_{max}}{1 + \left(\frac{\lambda}{k\varepsilon(0)} - 1 \right) e^{-\lambda t}} \quad (\text{A6})$$

Setting $\varepsilon(0) = \varepsilon_0$, we finally have:

$$\varepsilon(t) = \frac{\varepsilon_{max}}{1 + \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{max}}{\varepsilon_0} - 1 \right) e^{-\lambda t}} \quad (\text{A7})$$

From Equation (A7), we conclude that a larger value of λ corresponds to a steeper initial growth, meaning the system (e.g., wound closure) reaches saturation (i.e., ε_{max}) in a shorter time.

References

1. Elsdale, T.; Foley, R. Morphogenetic aspects of multilayering in petri dish cultures of human fetal lung fibroblasts. *J. Cell Biol.* **1969**, *41*, 298–311. [[CrossRef](#)]
2. Vařinková, M.; Krumnikl, M.; Gharibian, A.; Mičulek, O.; Kriegová, E.; Gajdoř, P. A novel method for evaluating and visualizing scratch wound healing assays using level-set and image sector analysis. *PNAS Nexus* **2025**, *4*, pgaf355. [[CrossRef](#)]
3. Jonkman, J.E.N.; Cathcart, J.; Xu, F.; Bartolini, P.; Amon, J.; Stevens, K.M.; Colarusso, P. An introduction to the wound healing assay using live-cell microscopy. *Cell Adhes. Migr.* **2014**, *8*, 440–451. [[CrossRef](#)]
4. Chung, H.H.; Bellefeuille, S.D.; Miller, H.N.; Gaborski, T.R. Extended live-tracking and quantitative characterization of wound healing and cell migration with SiR-Hoechst. *Exp. Cell Res.* **2018**, *373*, 198–210. [[CrossRef](#)]
5. Grada, A.; Otero-Vinas, M.; Prieto-Castrillo, F.; Obagi, Z.; Falanga, V. Research Techniques Made Simple: Analysis of Collective Cell Migration Using the Wound Healing Assay. *J. Investig. Dermatol.* **2017**, *137*, e11–e16. [[CrossRef](#)]
6. Liang, C.-C.; Park, A.Y.; Guan, J.-L. In vitro scratch assay: A convenient and inexpensive method for analysis of cell migration in vitro. *Nat. Protoc.* **2007**, *2*, 329–333. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

7. Francisco, M.; Ruiz-Espigares, J.; Gutiérrez-Naranjo, M.A.; Marchal, J.A. Using deep learning for predicting the dynamic evolution of breast cancer migration. *Comput. Biol. Med.* **2024**, *180*, 108890. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
8. Yu, L.Y.; Lin, H.C.; Hsu, C.L.; Kao, T.Y.; Tsai, F.C. Studying cell migration (random and wound healing) parameters with imaging and MATLAB analysis. *Bio Protoc.* **2023**, *13*, e4871. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
9. Cappiello, F.; Casciaro, B.; Mangoni, M.L. A novel in vitro wound healing assay to evaluate cell migration. *J. Vis. Exp.* **2018**, *133*, e56825.
10. Menon, M.B.; Ronkina, N.; Schwermann, J.; Kotlyarov, A.; Gaestel, M. Fluorescence-based quantitative scratch wound healing assay demonstrating the role of MAPKAP-K2/3 in fibroblast migration. *Cell Motil. Cytoskelet.* **2009**, *66*, 1041–1047. [[CrossRef](#)]
11. Srivastava, S.; Kinnunen, P.C.; Wang, Z.; Ho, K.K.Y.; Humphries, B.A.; Chen, S.; Linderman, J.J.; Luker, G.D.; Luker, K.E.; Garikipati, K. Inference of weak-form partial differential equations describing migration and proliferation mechanisms in wound healing experiments on cancer cells. *PLoS Comput. Biol.* **2025**, *21*, e1013607. [[CrossRef](#)]
12. Arora, G.; Singh, S.; Emadifar, H. Mathematical models of wound healing and tissue regeneration: Insights with numerical solution. *Innov. Discov.* **2024**, *1*, 13. [[CrossRef](#)]
13. Tsoularis, A.; Wallace, J. Analysis of logistic growth models. *Math. Biosci.* **2002**, *179*, 21–55. [[CrossRef](#)]
14. Hrytsiuk, P.; Parfeniuk, O.; Shevchenko, I. The logistic dynamics of population growth as a prerequisite for global sustainable development. *IOP Conf. Ser. Earth Environ. Sci.* **2023**, *1126*, 012030. [[CrossRef](#)]
15. Mathioudaki, E.; Rallis, M.; Politopoulos, K.; Alexandratou, E. Photobiomodulation and wound healing: Low-level laser therapy at 661 nm in a scratch assay keratinocyte model. *Ann. Biomed. Eng.* **2024**, *52*, 376–385. [[CrossRef](#)]
16. Avci, P.; Gupta, A.; Sadasivam, M.; Vecchio, D.; Pam, Z.; Pam, N.; Hamblin, M.R. Low-level laser (light) therapy (LLLT) in skin: Stimulating, healing, restoring. *Semin. Cutan. Med. Surg.* **2013**, *32*, 41–52.
17. Chung, H.; Dai, T.; Sharma, S.K.; Huang, Y.Y.; Carroll, J.D.; Hamblin, M.R. The nuts and bolts of low-level laser (light) therapy. *Ann. Biomed. Eng.* **2012**, *40*, 516–533. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
18. Gupta, A.; Avci, P.; Sadasivam, M.; Chandran, R.; Parizotto, N.; Vecchio, D.; de Melo, W.C.M.A.; Dai, T.; Chiang, L.Y.; Hamblin, M. Shining light on nanotechnology to help repair and regeneration. *Biotechnol. Adv.* **2013**, *31*, 607–631. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
19. Seaton, E.D.; Mouser, P.E.; Charakida, A.; Alam, S.; Seldon, P.E.; Chu, A.C. Investigation of the mechanism of action of nonablative pulsed-dye laser therapy in photorejuvenation and inflammatory acne vulgaris. *Br. J. Dermatol.* **2006**, *155*, 748–755. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
20. Mandel, A.; Hamblin, M.R. A renaissance in low-level laser (light) therapy—LLLT. *Photonics Lasers Med.* **2012**, *1*, 231–234. [[CrossRef](#)]
21. Farivar, S.; Malekshahabi, T.; Shiari, R. Biological effects of low-level laser therapy. *J. Lasers Med. Sci.* **2014**, *5*, 58–62.
22. AlGhamdi, K.M.; Kumar, A.; Moussa, N.A. Low-level laser therapy: A useful technique for enhancing the proliferation of various cultured cells. *Lasers Med. Sci.* **2012**, *27*, 237–249. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
23. Gupta, A.; Dai, T.; Hamblin, M. Effect of red and near-infrared wavelengths on low-level laser (light) therapy-induced healing of partial-thickness dermal abrasion in mice. *Lasers Med. Sci.* **2014**, *29*, 257–265. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
24. Kontomaris, S.V.; Stylianou, A.; Yova, D. Investigation of the mechanical properties of collagen fibrils under the influence of low power red laser irradiation. *Biomed. Phys. Eng. Express* **2016**, *2*, 064002. [[CrossRef](#)]
25. Chong, L.M.; Tng, D.J.H.; Tan, L.L.Y.; Chua, M.L.K.; Zhang, Y. Recent advances in radiation therapy and photodynamic therapy. *Appl. Phys. Rev.* **2021**, *8*, 041322. [[CrossRef](#)]
26. Zhang, Y.; Zhu, J.; Zhang, Z.; He, D.; Zhu, J.; Chen, Y.; Zhang, Y. Remodeling of tumor microenvironment for enhanced tumor chemodynamic/photothermal/chemotherapy. *J. Nanobiotechnol.* **2022**, *20*, 388. [[CrossRef](#)]
27. Brown, S.B.; Brown, E.A.; Walker, I. The present and future role of photodynamic therapy in cancer treatment. *Lancet Oncol.* **2004**, *5*, 497–508. [[CrossRef](#)]
28. Kontomaris, S.V.; Malamou, A.; Stylianou, A. The Young's modulus as a mechanical biomarker in AFM experiments: A tool for cancer diagnosis and treatment monitoring. *Sensors* **2025**, *25*, 3510. [[CrossRef](#)]
29. Huis In 't Veld, R.V.; Heuts, J.; Ma, S.; Cruz, L.J.; Ossendorp, F.A.; Jager, M.J. Current challenges and opportunities of photodynamic therapy against cancer. *Pharmaceutics* **2023**, *15*, 330. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
30. Chen, Q.; Yang, J.; Yin, H.; Li, Y.; Qiu, H.; Gu, Y.; Yang, H.; Xiaoxi, D.; Xiafei, S.; Che, B.; et al. Optimization of photobiomodulation therapy for wound healing of diabetic foot ulcers in vitro and in vivo. *Biomed. Opt. Express* **2022**, *13*, 2450–2466. [[CrossRef](#)]
31. Novak, J. Photobiomodulation: The use of specific light wavelengths to accelerate recovery, repair, and regeneration. In *Fundamentals of Recovery, Regeneration and Adaptation to Exercise Stress: An Integrated Approach*; Apostolopoulos, N.C., Bogdanis, G.C., Seagrave, L.R., Plyley, M.J., Eds.; Springer: Cham, Switzerland, 2025.
32. Topaloglu, N.; Ozdemir, M.; Cevik, Z.B.Y. Comparative analysis of the light parameters of red and near-infrared diode lasers to induce photobiomodulation on fibroblasts and keratinocytes: An in vitro study. *Photodermatol. Photoimmunol. Photomed.* **2021**, *37*, 253–262. [[CrossRef](#)]

33. Polemiodiotou, K.; Kulkarni, S.G.; Szydlak, R.; Lekka, M.; Radmacher, M.; Gkretsi, V.; Stylianopoulos, T.; Stylianou, A. Assessing sarcoma cell cytoskeleton remodeling in response to varying collagen concentration. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **2024**, *282*, 136770. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
34. Kijewski, T.; Kareem, A. On the reliability of a class of system identification techniques: Insights from bootstrap theory. *Struct. Saf.* **2002**, *24*, 261–280. [[CrossRef](#)]
35. Guo, L.; Dong, X.; Wang, R.; Dai, J.; Li, S.; Liu, L.; Kong, M.; Liu, Y.; Zhao, M.; Hui, X.; et al. PLAM system-mediated optimization of 808 nm low-level laser power density for enhanced bioactivity in human umbilical cord mesenchymal stem cells. *Opt. Lasers Eng.* **2025**, *194*, 109129. [[CrossRef](#)]
36. Crous, A.; Jansen Van Rensburg, M.; Abrahamse, H. Single and consecutive application of near-infrared and green irradiation modulates adipose derived stem cell proliferation and affect differentiation factors. *Biochimie* **2022**, *196*, 225–233. [[CrossRef](#)]
37. Etemadi, A.; Faghieh, A.; Chiniforush, N. Effects of photobiomodulation therapy with various laser wavelengths on proliferation of human periodontal ligament mesenchymal stem cells. *Photochem. Photobiol.* **2022**, *98*, 1182–1189. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
38. Szezerbaty, S.K.F.; De Oliveira, R.F.; Pires-Oliveira, D.A.A.; Soares, C.P.; Sartori, D.; Poli-Frederico, R.C. The effect of low-level laser therapy (660 nm) on the gene expression involved in tissue repair. *Lasers Med. Sci.* **2018**, *33*, 315–321.
39. Huang, Y.-Y.; Sharma, S.K.; Carroll, J.; Hamblin, M.R. Biphasic dose response in low level light therapy—An update. *Dose-Response* **2011**, *9*, 602–618.
40. Laffitte, C.; Sabino, V.; Rosado, M.; de Carvalho, V.L.A.; Miguel, M.C.d.C.; de Moura, C.E.B.; Barboza, C.A.G. Effect of nutritional stress and photobiomodulation protocol on in vitro viability and proliferation of murine preosteoblast cells. *Lasers Med. Sci.* **2024**, *39*, 289. [[CrossRef](#)]
41. Roets, B.; Abrahamse, H.; Crous, A. Three-dimensional cell culture of adipose-derived stem cells in a hydrogel with photobiomodulation augmentation. *J. Vis. Exp.* **2024**, e66616. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

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